

SECTION OF HUMANITIES AND PHILOLOGY

HERMENEUTICS OF INTERPERSONAL COMMUNICATION ON THE INTERNET

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Abstract

This paper examines the application of Hans-Georg Gadamer's hermeneutic categories to the analysis of virtual interpersonal communication in the process of interactions on the internet. The author applies to the study of interpersonal communication such hermeneutic categories as: historically effected consciousness, subject matter, hermeneutic question, fore-structure of understanding, hermeneutic circle and fusion of horizon.

The paper consists of three parts, among which the introduction deals with advantages and disadvantages of both philosophical and digital hermeneutics. Digital humanities require new methods of research, thus hermeneutics in the digital space is still relevant. Philosophical hermeneutics based on Gadamer's theory, realizes deep research across a great variety of phenomena in the field of digital humanities.

The second part gives a hermeneutic view of internet interactions and how hermeneutic categories can be applied to the analysis of virtual interpersonal communication. The contemporary era has changed the situation of interpersonal interaction, in that the hermeneutic situation occurs in virtual reality mediated by computers and other technical devices. The author comes to the conclusion that the hermeneutics of interpersonal communication methodologically has been modified. From that point of view not only digital codes but also philosophical hermeneutic categories still are relevant and can be applied to practice and research.

Keywords: philosophical hermeneutics, digital hermeneutics, interpersonal communication, internet interactions, hermeneutics categories, virtual, digital space.

Introduction. Philosophical or Digital Hermeneutics.

Comprehension and interpretation from a simple conversation to the level of intercultural or global communication, have been the field of study for more than century ago and hermeneutics as the art of interpretation and a philosophical approach to human understanding has been among the leading methodologies of inquiry. The dialogic nature of human understanding is a prominent research area in Hans-Georg Gadamer's philosophical hermeneutics. Dialogue is considered by Gadamer, one of the most famous German philosopher of the 20th century, as a fundamental existential phenomenon of being and an essential feature of human existence (Gadamer 1999). This paper examines the application of Hans-Georg Gadamer's hermeneutic categories to the analysis of virtual interpersonal communication.

Gadamer expressed his ideas in his main work "Truth and Method". His theory includes the following concepts: the centrality of the subject matter, hermeneutic question, the fore-structure of understanding, the hermeneutic circle, the fusion of horizons and etc. Gadamer's hermeneutics describes the whole system of categories generally related to the concept of historically effected consciousness (Gadamer 1999), constituent terms of which will be applied to the study of virtual interpersonal communication. Among the other well-known hermeneutic categories one of the most important is "genuine conversation" (Gadamer 1986), manifestation of which is typical for face to face dialogues. The aim of this paper is to analyze whether a hermeneutic genuine conversation in the internet specific realm is possible and discover how the digital environment modifies its features in virtual interpersonal communication.

As for the present study it is necessary to specify the definite terms and notions. Computational turn in our everyday life brings digital technologies to hermeneutic methodology, where new issues from the point of view of internet reality are bound to arise. Hermeneutics is usually associated with the study of what makes sense. Meaningfulness is understood not only as what it is written or said, but also what actions and various human activities mean – all these require interpretation. It goes without saying that hermeneutics both philosophical and digital are used for understanding new perception of social experience on the internet.

In scientific literature not long ago there appeared a new term "digital hermeneutics". As A. Romele, M. Severo, P. Furia stress "*Methodological hermeneutics does not represent a unitary field either. Some academics, usually with a background in linguistic or digital humanities, affirm or implicitly admit that digital hermeneutics is about computer-mediated interpretation and understanding of texts or texts corpora, or about a texts reading-inspired attitude towards elements of digitality such as the code*" (Romele, Severo and Furia 2018, p. 5).

As the authors write, digital humanities require new methods of research, thus hermeneutics in the digital space is still relevant and is used because it presupposes not only computer mediated interpretation but also analyzes the great variety of aspects of people's activities on the internet.

Different authors concentrate on different aspects of the interpretations of digital objects. Thus, the question is whether digital hermeneutics can be applied to research in humanities, because the interpretation of codes is not the dominated issue of hermeneutics, speaking in the broad context not only codes but also the human contexts of ideas and traditions are should

also be interpreted and understood. As R. Capurro has shown:

“Digital hermeneutics observes how the digital code is being interpreted and implemented (or not) in the globalized societies of the twenty-first century. It deals with all processes related with the digital network at the social level, autonomous systems of interpretation, communication and interaction (robotics) as well as all kind of hybrid biological systems (bionics) and digital manipulation at the nano level. This broad spectrum of phenomena can be restricted, for practical purposes, to the study of social systems of interpretation and social construction of meaning based on the Internet or on what we now call Web 2.0” (Capurro 2010).

I agree with these words and with the application of hermeneutic ideas to virtual interpersonal interactions as part of social reality, since they are able to highlight social aspects of human beings. Digital databases or robotics interactions should be specified to a certain area of research in the context of digital hermeneutics, because in these cases digital hermeneutics is considered more as technological process, since it proposes technical solutions and is applied in interpretational machines. A. Romele, M. Severo, P. Furia also make the distinction in digital hermeneutics between qualitative and quantitative approaches (Romele, Severo and Furia 2018). Digital hermeneutics in its quantitative methods deals with virtual objects, electronic literature, and databases and is applied to computer sciences, while its qualitative approach can be applied to the study of interpersonal communication on the internet, including blogs, forums, Facebook, Instagram, Twitter, WeChat accounts and so on.

Classical (philosophical) hermeneutics based on Gadamer’s theory, realizes deep research across a great variety of phenomena in the field of digital humanities, among them electronic literature, virtual interpersonal communication, printed literature and many other cultural objects. For example, F. Frabetti remarks on the idea of a re-conceptualization of digital humanities that indeed transcends an assumed dichotomy between the technical and the cultural aspects (Frabetti, 2012). The same aspect is stressed by J.J. van Zundert, who writes about a hermeneutic qualitative approach to interpretation in digital humanities (Zundert 2016). Cultural objects together with the presence of the creative mind of their authors, or communicators involvement should be hermeneutically interpreted and analyzed.

Interpersonal communication on the internet: a hermeneutic view

Interpersonal dialogue is used as a means for establishing personal contacts and friendly relationship and has great impact in a society. An interlocutor in a face to face interaction can raise the questions like “How does the dialogue partner perceive the situation of this dialogue?” or “Can the participant understand me well?” His or her expectations are based on their previous experience with other members of the same social group or community. In the digital space hermeneutic categories for the analysis of human interactions are applied to uncover specific characteristics of interpersonal communication on the internet.

Historically effected consciousness. If communicators are involved in a trustworthy atmosphere and genuine conversation, it can be studied from the point of view of hermeneutics. Gadamer’s hermeneutics contains the whole system of principles generally known as the concept of “historically effected consciousness” and it is closely connected with his theory of hermeneutic experience and the fore-structure of understanding. Gadamer expresses that:

“Long before we understand ourselves through the process of self-examination, we understand ourselves in a self-evident way in the family, society, and state in which we live. The focus of subjectivity is a distorting mirror. The self-awareness of the individual is only a flickering in the closed circuits of historical life. That is why the prejudices of the individual, far more than his judgments, constitute the historical reality of his being” (Gadamer 1999, p. 276-277)

A person who is involved in digital communication can have false and true prejudices, his perception can be under the influence of past experience, background knowledge and historical and/or cultural traditions. But being in a virtual reality, it is very difficult to overcome the great amount of information, which is why the first stage of preparation for understanding what is happening in a virtual reality does not refer to self reflection process. The reasons for this may be any of the following:

- the change of images is noticed faster than in the usual state of consciousness, which is difficult to keep track of;
- there is no traditional division into more or less important, which makes it difficult to fix attention and orientation in the virtual space;
- there is no spatial and temporal continuum, familiar to us in the virtual world.

Moreover, prejudices, pre-understanding and traditions in general can be unknown because of anonymity and the challenge of shifting sex, age, social position, etc. Background knowledge and traditional pre-judgements in the case of identity modification can be very vague and indefinite. Internet suggests many opportunities and platforms making easy to interrupt traditions as information society and digital technologies produce rapid change of standards, rules and customs. Hermeneutics in the era of the internet instead of historically effected consciousness rather analyzes the reasons for the changes in traditions and prejudices.

At the same time I do not follow the idea of R. Capurro, who remarks:

“I believe that we live in an age in which the sense of Being is widely interpreted from a digital perspective as the ‘Zeitgeist’ of post-industrial societies. From this perspective I also question what one could call a digital humanism that would look for the limits of the digital within the realm of the human. The reason for this is that digital technology allows a desubjectivation of human processes of interpretation without being necessarily opposed to them. This means a dehumanization of hermeneutics as far as, for instance, biological processes can be seen as processes of interaction and communication based on the genetic code that can be itself object of human manipulation” (Capurro 2010).

In the wider context of the concepts and terms, the usage of digital hermeneutics can be divided in two directions; one of them applied to the analysis of the so-called databases in the proper sense of the word, the second one – methodology for all human activities on the internet, including interpersonal communication, reading and interpretation of texts, cultural artefacts, etc.

Subject matter and question. Gadamer also emphasizes the priority of question in interpersonal communication, where the direct answer leads to another possible question. A good question is considered by Gadamer as a good conversational starter, and among the best conversational questions are specified open-ended ones that activate and interrogate the mind. Interesting questions make the partner think of something in detail and express it in more than two or three utterances. A good conversation goes on simultaneously, taking into consideration heuristic questions.

It is generally assumed that hermeneutic question is more than an interrogation but is a reflection of the partners' intention to elaborate their shared views and understanding. Hermeneutic questions in virtual interpersonal communication are no longer true conversational starters or inner mechanism because they don't reflect ontological characteristics of dialectical question-answer unity in the dialogical process, but become formal signs of digital interactions.

Subject matter (*die Sache*) also meets the challenges of digital communication. Subject matter is more or less obvious in videoconferences, organizational events or the online educational process in university classes. Messages may not fix definite issues, they can rapidly transform from one topic to another, from the first point to the second one, to a third and further points appear chaotically as it often occurs in group chats. The structure of the messages no longer includes the subject matter, i.e. the premise guiding any understanding. The unity of meaning is not ready to be achieved as the virtual interlocutors may not mean the same thing or, follow the same subject of conversation. The interlocutors do not focus attention on the conversation's logic, they are faced with spontaneity and objectification as typical characteristics of a virtual event, therefore they don't realize responsibility and engagement in virtual interpersonal dialogue. This dialogue consists of fragments, episodes, interrupted utterances which do not comprise the whole picture of conversational interaction.

Hermeneutic circle: anticipation and perception. Interpretation takes place in the communication process, and it happens successfully depending on the level of anticipation and involvement. Agreement concerning the subject matter refers the communicators to anticipation of the whole. Then, in a classical hermeneutic approach the analysis points out the relevance of a very important category. This is the hermeneutic circle, which explicates circular movement of understanding, - it goes from the parts to the whole conversation and then again to another level.

In virtual interpersonal communication it is possible to meet the expectations, but it cannot be hermeneutically estimated as there is no evidence of sincere and

true mind participation in the dialogue. But the conversation doesn't unveil historical horizons with national customs, heritage and traditions, national world outlook in general, so that the interlocutors cannot place themselves in the other's position, they cannot evaluate the other person's nature. The horizon of anticipation doesn't give them the opportunity to go beyond their false prejudices, to look at the subject matter from another angle of vision.

The circle consists of the whole and its parts, develops the process of extraction of information and getting meaning from digital resources or chatting groups in internet communities. It also has been transformed by the actions of using techniques in the digital network, no longer a dialectic unity because anticipation in the hermeneutic sense of the word does not lead to understanding of ourselves, but to getting more amount of information and knowledge.

Summing up the observation, it is clear that hermeneutic circle has no longer the circular moving process, it changes its principle from the rounding development of interpretational process to a one-level movement within a circle.

Fusion of horizons. On the internet understanding as the achievement of fusion of horizons is also obscure. Instead of listening there is a mediated with computers technical process, where interlocutors can observe the screen, emerging or appearing images, lines, words, expressions, and can hear noise and technical interference.

Virtual interpersonal communication does not presuppose hermeneutic understanding in each case of interactions. Internet platforms very often are used to get information, therefore functioning on the semantic level, so dialogues become much more formal and simple. H. Klein and K. Lyytinen point to the same idea:

"They apply the Gadamerian metaphor of "fusion of horizons" to data modelling in the sense of capturing some of the meanings intended by the users but alien to the developers who must translate them into some appropriate formalism and re-translate into the user's horizons in order to become part of their everyday practices" (Klein and Lyytinen 1992, p. 214)

In the era of information technologies, fusion of horizons for human beings in new forms and transformed ways of conversations is still relevant. Separately taken statements don't give the possibility to develop the inner logic of the conversation in order to achieve its unity. Gadamer analyzes the conversation through dialectics in order to reach not only the common meaning, but to underline the importance of their reflection upon the very sense and significance of communication for their existence.

Conclusion.

Hermeneutic categories applied to the study of virtual interpersonal conversations modify their meaning and are realized in the ways that the computer mediated process impact on them. Internet reality dissolves human beings' identities and individuals face the same challenge in attempting to learn the huge amount of information and opportunities, as the result they face in shifting their identities.

Interpersonal atmosphere of the so-called “genuine dialogue” is no longer the space of the fusion of horizons. As we can see, hermeneutic dimensions of virtual interpersonal dialogues change their content and meaning: traditions, and fore-structure of understanding are no more characteristics of subjective vision, hermeneutic circle is not always led by anticipation and does not develop the cognition process, the fusion of horizons does not by all means takes place on the Internet. R. Capurro remarks the same ideas:

“The hermeneutic circle as a key metaphor of philosophic hermeneutics should be re-interpreted as a hermeneutic network. This leads to a change of another core idea of hermeneutics, namely the Gadamerian “fusion of horizons” (Gadamer 1975, p. 284). It is not only a “fusion” but a “linking” that characterizes the relationship between the messengers of the digital network that need to call each other through what system theory calls the “meaning offer.” (Capurro 2010).

Contemporary society still needs to understand itself as human beings in a virtual communication process. In a digital globalized world advanced technologies including AI will continue to be the tools for people, which is why human beings will need to reflect upon their existence and the sense of life in the 21st century. Who are we as members of society in our local communities and at a global level in the era of digital and network communication? The answer to this question incorporate hermeneutic principles, which unveils our own self-understanding in the context of existential dimensions of dialogues.

Hermeneutic methodology should be applied more to the analysis of internet interactions because hermeneutics contains certain advantages: it reveals the deep possibilities of human existence, explores the intentionality of the communication process and helps overcome chaotic and fragmentary speech interactions.

We realize that we are all engaged in a new intellectual computer based practice, and computers, smartphones and other devices have become part of our lives. In this emergent digital environment human beings should realize the importance of self-reflection

upon the ontological foundation of our activities in the virtual space, human beings cannot be primitive digital objects and lose their existential characteristics. From that point of view not only digital codes but also philosophical hermeneutic categories can be applied to practice and research. Virtual social activities, the search for information, interpersonal communication – all of these are full of meaning and represent social systems of interpretation and they all pursue social construction of understanding on the internet.

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